

HISTORY AND CLASSIFICATION OF NATIONAL INSTRUMENTS

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Abstract: Interest in Uzbek folk instruments and their research began in ancient times. The article talks about the history and classification of national musical instruments. Information is provided about the research of musicologists who have shown zeal in collecting and studying traditional Uzbek music.

Key words: national musical instrument, classification, traditional music, encyclopedist, ethnography.

Introduction.

The history of Uzbek folk dances has been studied since ancient times. In a number of works of scholars of the Central Asian region of the 9th-17th centuries, music and dances and their description, musicians who gained fame in their time, names of famous music and works are given.

Since the 70s of the 19th century, the study and study of Uzbek traditional music began to be carried out at a rapid pace. These works were mainly carried out by harbieu kapelmeusters. In addition to working in the orchestra, they were also engaged in composing folklore works. The creators who decided to study the history of Uzbek folk dances are A. Euxhorn and F. Leusik. As a result of A. Euxhorn's research, a catalog of 36 folk dances belonging to different groups was compiled. The famous composer, ethnographer and pedagogue V. A. Uspenskiu also performed extensive work on the study and collection of folk dances. As a result of his active participation and action, in 1919, a music-ethnographic department was established in Tashkent, and he himself headed this department. During the activity of the department, he was engaged in gathering a collection of folk dances and studying their performance possibilities.

In the history of studying Uzbek music, V. M. Beluauev, a large-scale scientist, talented folklorist, and pedagogue, has made great contributions. The materials of V. A. Uspenskiu's research in the territory of Turkmenistan between 1925-1926 served as an important source for V. M. Beluauev's study of Eastern music and culture. In the study of music theory, V. M. Beluauev emphasizes the importance of treatises on music by Eastern scientists. His researches in the department of the history of the development of Uzbek folk dances, their classification and measurement are of great interest.

In 1933, V. M. Beluauev's book "Musical dances of Uzbekistan" was published in Moscow. It contains descriptions of more than 50 species. In the book, for the first time, Uzbek folk dances are scientifically classified. In conclusion, the author concluded: in order to widely use Uzbek folk songs in the development of music and culture, it is necessary to improve them and add notation. F.M. Karomatov conducted research on the issues of studying and teaching

traditional musical instruments, and A.I. Petrosuans conducted research on the quality repair and modernization of instruments. A.I. Petrosuans, in the book "Instrumental Studies", in addition to scientifically justifying the basic groups and classification of folk instruments, described the families of instrument groups and described their structure, technical and artistic possibilities¹. Practical tips are also given for their effective use in performance.

An educational method was formed in the mobaun of long boys. As a result of careful repair and improvement of folk dances, technical methods of sound creation and performance skills were developed. As a result of the transition from the listening method of playing the instrument to the method of playing it on sheet music, as well as a lot of work on the educational repertoire, the establishment of performance schools in folk instruments came to the fore. Development of methods and didactic foundations of teaching folk dance performers was carried out in the same direction. Over the years, a number of fundamental textbooks, training manuals and collections have been published by the professors-teachers of the Department of "Folk Music" under the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan. Performance schools were formed in folk dances. At the same time, training manuals and monographs on the organization and work of the folk music orchestra were published. In this way, the basics of the initial stage of music education were formed based on the use of folk dances. Every student should have broad general education and professional knowledge during the school year. Because, as we all know, many of our graduates connect their lives with pedagogical activity. This requires a good understanding of psychology, pedagogy, and methodology, as well as having a broad outlook. However, general and individual methods based on the principles of pedagogy, increasing the uniqueness of education, and representing the achievements of performance culture have not been developed. Most of the published textbooks and manuals refer to education in a narrow sense. All the instructions are related to the state of performance, technical methods of sound creation, mastery of performance, educational procedures and pedagogical ethics. However, less attention has been paid to the importance of education, the use of education, science, and other relevant issues. The lack of development of this method in higher educational institutions has a negative effect on the quality of education and pedagogical efficiency in the field of performing arts. From the pedagogical point of view, the concept of methodology is used in two different ways:

1. *Methodology - a theoretical course conducted in school, as an academic subject;*
2. *Methodology - as the method and forms of teaching.*

When talking about methodology, the basis of education should be derived from the combination of objective and subjective factors. The method is based on the study of the effective methods of educational practice, it is learned as a result of practical application and generalization in the process of scientific-theoretical research. As a result, two basic methods emerge: the general method and the special method. General methodology deals with the study of specific features and laws of the educational process.

Different from the general method, the special method develops the methods and forms of the faster acquisition of special knowledge skills. The improvement of performance methods in folk dances can be divided into the following main steps:

1. In-depth study of modern general and musical pedagogy, psychology and didactic issues.
2. Study and summarize the results of special methods, teaching experiences.

3. Critical analysis of schools and trends, as a result of which, development of modern principles of educational development.

Conclusion.

Based on the above comments, we should emphasize that today, the method of teaching Uzbek folk songs that meets the modern requirements is separate for each stage of education (primary, secondary, higher). , we can ensure the quality of professionalism only by adapting it in a unique way and using the literature of the next generation in the future. Music schools, specialized art schools and higher education institutions need to solve the issues of forming the culture of performing arts by creating educational programs that can fully meet these modern requirements.

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